

D2.3 FINAL RDA RESULTS, ADOPTION & TAKE-UP REPORT

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Abstract	The final of two reports that tracks the adoption take-up, that has been achieved within RDA Europe 4.0 within the communities, existing & new.

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

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Introduction and Executive Summary

This report describes take-up and adoption of work produced by RDA and, more specifically, the role of the RDA Europe 4.0 project in promoting such take-up and adoption. It is the second of two reports which will cover this topic; the first version, D2.1 RDA Results, Adoption and take-up report, was delivered in May 2019.

The Research Data Alliance has 43 Recommendations and Supporting Outputs, 8 of which are officially acknowledged as ICT Technical Specifications. There are also several more Recommendations and Supporting Outputs in the process of endorsement. A full list can be seen on the RDA website using the RDA's new Recommendations and Outputs catalogue tool.¹

A number of actions have been taken by the RDA Europe project to increase the adoption of outputs, including:

- A successful open call to award grants to adoption projects;
- Increasing the volume of published Adoption Stories online, including the introduction of new audiovisual Adoption Stories;
- Facilitating the publication of articles in the CODATA Data Science Journal Special Collection on RDA Results;
- Promoting and disseminating RDA use cases by illustrating examples in webinars, plenary sessions, and in the RDA Global Adoption Week in June 2020.

In addition, cascading grants directed toward RDA Europe Ambassadors for disciplines and in the establishment of RDA National Nodes have played a role in fostering the take-up of RDA results. The RDA Secretariat also convened a Global Adoption Task Force during the RDA Europe 4.0 project period, which has worked with organisations who have implemented RDA Outputs in order to produce use cases for supporting adoption and has actively tracked the uptake of outputs throughout the duration of the RDA Europe 4.0 project.

Details of all of these activities are described in the sections which follow.

Supporting European Take-up and Adoption

Adoption of new processes and technologies can bring a number of challenges, including cost implications, resource management concerns, and uncertainty over where to begin. Promoting the implementation of its outputs is one of the goals of the RDA; earlier RDA Europe projects recognised that being able to draw on the experiences of others plays a vital role in facilitating the adoption and implementation of RDA Recommendations and Outputs. In response to this, previous RDA Europe projects provided adoption grants as a means to stimulate the take-up and adoption of RDA outputs and recommendations and to overcome this barrier. This work has been continued and refined in the current RDA Europe 4.0 project.

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/catalogue>

RDA Europe Adoption Grants

Following an Adoption Open Call in 2019², the RDA Europe 4.0 project initially funded eight organisations to adopt one or more existing RDA recommendations and/or outputs. These adoption grant projects were intended to provide a valuable testbed for the adoption of a range of RDA Recommendations and Outputs and to disseminate their projects to as wide an audience as possible as adoption use cases.

The call for adoption grants opened in December 2018 and closed in March 2019. A total amount of €120,000 was allocated in the project budget, permitting 8 projects of up to €15,000 each. The project used a range of mechanisms to promote the call³. As well as promotion through social media and on the website, the call was promoted in the RDA Newsletter, it featured in presentations given by project staff, and was publicised by RDA national nodes to their members through their RDA web pages and local mailing lists. A webinar was held on 21st February 2019 to promote the call. The Digital Curation Centre (UEDIN) presented the programme and gave advice to prospective applicants. Presentations were also given by DANS and VADMC on their adoption cases, and a Q&A session was moderated at the end. 43 participants attended; slides and video are available on the RDA website.⁴

13 applications for these grants were received from nine different countries. A strong range of proposals were put forward, covering a variety of outputs and disciplines. Eight awards were made and announced on the RDA site, as well as promoted via social media.⁵ The eight original recipients are listed below in Table 1.

Table 1: Accepted Grant application projects

Project title	Organisation, Country	Recommendation(s)/Output(s) adopted
23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management	SURFsara, Netherlands	23 Things: Libraries For Research Data

² The details about the RDA Europe 4.0 open calls are reported in D1.5 Cascading Grant Report Management.

³ A complete description of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken by the RDA Europe 4.0 project will be reported in D4.4 RDA Europe global communications strategy and in D5.5 Final Communication, Marketing & Stakeholders Engagement report.

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/what-why-and-how-rda-europe-40-adoption-grants-0>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/top-european-organisations-funded-adopt-rda-recommendations-and-outputs>

From Portal To PIDs: Creating Persistent Identifiers For MERIL-2 RI Entries	European Science Foundation, France	Persistent identifiers: Consolidated assertions
Implementing a data publishing workflow model for research data sharing in ICTP	Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Italy	Data Type Model and Registry Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data
A Road to a Hungarian Data Publishing Policy	University of Debrecen and Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Hungary	Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues
CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation Service	Climate Change Centre Austria, Austria	Scalable Dynamic-data Citation Methodology
Improving the Copernicus Climate Data Store metadata scheme with the “RDA metadata standards repository”	Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, Spain	Metadata Standards Directory
Template for reproducible, shareable and achievable data analysis	Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, Spain	Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components
A model of data integration related to wheat genetic resources and resistance to Fusarium head blight	Sofia University Saint Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria	Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines, Ontologies and User Cases

Of the original eight projects who were selected to receive grants, two were unable to continue with their projects. The first of these was the 'From Portal To PIDs: Creating Persistent Identifiers For MERIL-2 RI Entries' project, based at the European Science Foundation (ESF), which decided after the grant was awarded that they would not be able to contribute the co-funding for the project. This was confirmed with the original grant down-payment repaid by ESF following confirmation. The second of the projects to withdraw was 'Implementing a data publishing workflow model for research data sharing in ICTP', based at the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP). The reason for their withdrawal was due to the fact that, as an organisation part-funded by UNESCO, they could not be audited by the European Commission. Though there was a significant amount of effort made by the RDA Europe 4.0 project to work around this, ultimately the ICTP could not accept the grant stipulations and had to withdraw in March 2020. Figure 1 below maps out the countries who were awarded adoption grants along with the logos of the lead organisations. Worth noting here is the fact that two of the grants, to the projects based at the University of Sofia and the joint project at the Hungarian Academy of Sciences and the University of Debrecen, were awarded to Eastern European countries, addressing a point raised by Commission reviewers about the need to engage with communities in this area.

Figure 1: Map of countries awarded Adoption Grant

A summary of each of the eight funded projects was included in the D2.1 RDA Results, Adoption and Take-up report submitted in month 15 of the RDA Europe 4.0 project.⁶ A dedicated page for the funded projects was set up on the RDA website,⁷ which included a brief summary of each of the funded projects as well as a link to an introductory blog written by the RDA Europe project team and promoted via regular RDA communications channels; these are described in more detail below.

Each of the grantees were required to deliver interim and final project activity reports to the RDA Europe 4.0 project partners for internal use, submit an RDA Adoption Story, and to conduct at least one recorded webinar presentation on their project. The interim and final reports were delivered by each of the grantees in months 25 and 29 of the project respectively. The grantees have until the close of the project on 30th September 2020 to deliver their Adoption Story (one has been submitted and published to date by the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre project⁸). All projects have conducted their webinar presentations and at the time of writing are going through the editing process, to be published and promoted on the RDA site when available.

In order to chart the mutual benefits to both the RDA and the funded projects of taking part in the Adoption Grant scheme, it is useful here to look at the areas in which the projects achieved results, rather than at individual projects in isolation. This cross-cutting approach gives a better overall view of the impact of the grant scheme and makes it possible to draw out further suggestions that can be used to inform strategies around the promotion of RDA results in the future. In the sections below, the advantage to the projects of their engagement with the RDA and the benefits of the cascading grant scheme to the RDA are described.

How funded adoption projects leveraged the RDA

Community input

In their final project activity reports, a number of grantees noted how they were able to leverage the RDA community to provide input on their projects. This was in the form of writing sprint sessions, user testing of new services, and presentations designed to gather attendee feedback, among others. For other grantees, community input was not a key component; however, it is clear that connections with the RDA community still played a role in progressing these projects.

The gathering of community input was the key influence in the development of an online version of the '23 Things' tool as part of the SURFsara project. This tool, of which development is ongoing, is designed to allow users to search the linked resources by audience, theme, and data lifecycle stage.⁹ Though it was not planned in the original description of work in the grant application, the idea of an online tool was suggested and supported enthusiastically by the sprint session audiences. The audiences for these sessions were not made up exclusively of RDA members,

⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/what-why-and-how-rda-europe-40-adoption-grants-0>

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/rda-europe-adoption-grants>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/improving-copernicus-climate-data-store-metadata-scheme-rda-metadata-standards-repository>

⁹ <https://23things.sites.uu.nl/>

but sessions run by the SURFsara team at RDA Sweden and Lithuania node events, at the International Digital Curation Conference in February 2020 in Dublin, Ireland, and five sessions of various types at the RDA Helsinki Plenary 14 event each each had strong input from RDA members, which resulted positively in the development of the 23 Things tool.

Further positive impact of RDA community input on one of the funded projects was apparent in the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) project to develop a reproducible paper framework (called 'Maneage'). Of note in this project is how the RDA community was used to gather technical input. Specifically, the project lead, Dr Mohammad Akhlaghi presented at an RDA 'Ask me Anything' webinar in November 2019 on the progress of the project up to that point.¹⁰ One of the outcomes of this session was for four non-astronomy researchers who are RDA members to agree to use and test the Maneage template extensively and provide feedback. The community connections afforded by the RDA here allowed the project to ensure that the Maneage template is suitable across a wide variety of domains.

The RDA community was also of benefit to grantees whose projects did not explicitly require input or feedback from outside sources.

- In its efforts to continue the work that began prior to RDA Europe 4.0, the Climate Change Centre Austria's (CCCA) application of the Data Citation Working Group Recommendation resulted in a high level of cooperation between the CCCA and the Working Group co-chairs, with the CCCA's work presented at the WG's session at the Helsinki Plenary 14 event.
- The project at the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC) relied on the efforts of the RDA community with respect to the RDA metadata standards repository. This resource is maintained by the RDA Metadata Standards Directory Working Group¹¹, with this maintenance affording projects like the BSC one to use it in the selection and application of metadata standards.

Communications, promotion, and dissemination

In their final project activity reports, grantees were asked to provide details on any communications, promotion and dissemination activities they conducted to raise awareness of the work in which they were engaged. It is clear from these reports that the various modes of communication afforded by the RDA Europe 4.0 project and the RDA community more broadly provided support to the grantees and featured heavily in their dissemination plans.

At the outset of the projects, the RDA Europe 4.0 project partners decided to opt for a blog series to introduce each of the projects to the wider RDA community. This decision was made as the mandatory deliverables mentioned above (namely the Adoption Stories and recorded webinars) would not be produced until close to the end of the RDA Europe 4.0 project. The UEDIN produced this series; a draft of the blog posts were produced and shared with each of the grants to check for accuracy, then published and promoted via the RDA's social media channels. These blogs

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/understanding-reproducibility-crisis-and-funding-opportunities-ecrs>

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-standards-directory-working-group.html>

were produced in order to highlight each project individually to a general audience. They were intended to provide some background information of the organisations adopting the Recommendations/Outputs, the issues they were addressing by implementing them, and how the RDA was of benefit to their organisation and project. The blogs are linked to each project on the RDA Europe Adoption Grants website page.¹²

Other means by which the projects have been promoted included the RDA Global Adoption Week and the CODATA Data Science Journal Special Collection for RDA Results. These are covered in more detail later in this report.

As mentioned above, the SURFsara project was able to take advantage of events organised by RDA National Nodes in the dissemination of its activities. Other grantees took the opportunity to present at events organised by the RDA National Node network. These included:

- Presentations by the BSC and IAC projects at an RDA Spain webinar in July 2020, details of which are available along with the recording of the session;¹³
- A talk given by the University of Sofia project at an RDA Bulgaria event on Data Management in July 2020;¹⁴
- Close cooperation between the RDA Hungary National Node and Hungarian adoption project for an ongoing presentation series at NI4OS-Europe.¹⁵

The D3.5 Coordination of National Nodes Framework report (to be published in M31 of the RDA Europe 4.0 project) will cover in more detail the activities of the RDA National Node network and how they have engaged with their local communities.

In terms of the take-up and adoption of RDA results, having in place clear requirements for the communications outcomes expected of the grantees, along with support from the RDA Europe project partners and National Node network for dissemination and promotion, has resulted in increased awareness of the impact of the RDA in general and in concrete use cases to demonstrate the value of RDA results for those dealing with data in varying roles and disciplines. In the next section, the impact that the grant programme has had in terms of the benefits to the RDA is examined.

How the Adoption Grant scheme was of benefit to RDA

Implementation of RDA results across project types and disciplines

The projects funded as part of the Adoption Grant scheme were each in various stages of development and concerned a wide range of activities. Three of the grants were issued to projects whose work was a continuation of efforts begun prior to the start of the award period. The grants

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/rda-europe-adoption-grants>.

¹³ Event details and recordings: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/rda-spain/post/rda-webinar-future-open-science-initiatives-spain-9-july-2020>; <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/rda-spain/post/rda-spain-webinar-recording-available>

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-bulgaria-node-workshop-data-management>

¹⁵ <https://ni4os.eu/2020/07/07/virtual-introduction-of-ni4os-europe-efforts-for-open-science-in-hungary/>

awarded to CCCA, BSC, and IAC allowed for projects which were already established to be developed further with the implementation of RDA Recommendations and Outputs.

- As mentioned above, the project at CCCA built on earlier work which had involved Recommendations produced by the RDA Data Citation Working Group.
- BSC's project was part of a wider initiative on the implementation of a quality control process at the Copernicus Climate Change Service's Climate Data Store.¹⁶
- The grant awarded to the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias concerned the further development of the reproducible template first designed in 2016.

As well as being concerned with ongoing projects, the funding also allowed for the update of an existing RDA Output. Taking the '23 Things' output, the SURFsara project initially set out to develop audience-specific 'Things' resources for the communities it identified. However, as referenced above, this project broadened its aims to later begin the construction of an online tool for 'Things' resources.

The final two grants were concerned with the initial steps in the projects' activities. The awards to the projects at the University of Sofia and shared between the University of Debrecen and the Hungarian Academy of Sciences also addressed points raised by the RDA Europe 4.0 project reviewers in connection with focusing the open calls on regions with less RDA participation and less developed policies for open and interoperable data. Both of these projects began at around the same time as their respective national nodes were established by another RDA Europe 4.0 grant, strengthening the RDA's presence in these countries.

The grantees also engaged a broad range of disciplines and other stakeholders, as displayed in Table 2 below (disciplines listed here are based on their responses in their final project activity reports):

Table 2: Disciplines and stakeholders engaged as part of Adoption Grants

Project title	Disciplines and stakeholders engaged
23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management	PhD candidates, Bachelor & Master students, Data librarians, Subject librarians, Data stewards, IT support, IT specialists, Research software engineers, Policy makers
A Road to a Hungarian Data Publishing Policy	Data repository staff, Librarians, Data librarians
CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation Service	Climate science, Meteorological science, Geoscience, Physics, Computer science, IT

¹⁶ <https://www.bsc.es/research-and-development/projects/c3s512-copernicus-project>

Improving the Copernicus Climate Data Store metadata scheme with the “RDA metadata standards repository”	Data science, IT, Climate science, Atmospheric science
Maneage: Template for reproducible, shareable and achievable data analysis	Astrophysics, Biophysics, Ecology, Visualisation, Data Science, Research support
A model of data integration related to wheat genetic resources and resistance to Fusarium head blight	Computer science, Bioinformatics, Plant protection, Plant molecular biology

It is also worth noting here that the Maneage template¹⁷ developed as part of the IAC grant has been used for the analysis of a paper on COVID-19 research, demonstrating the impact that this project has already had.¹⁸ Further publication of papers are expected from the four researchers who assisted in testing and providing feedback on Maneage.

The wide range of disciplines engaged and the variety in the types of projects funded points to the impact that this grant scheme made in terms of engaging communities and promoting RDA the practical applications of RDA Recommendations and Outputs.

Promotion of RDA within national communities

As noted above, the local environments of the funded projects are in differing stages of development in terms of maturity of open science policies and practices, as well as RDA activity. Despite this, each served as a vehicle to promote the RDA and RDA results in their local communities. Two of the projects in particular were concerned with engaging local researchers and research support staff.

- One of the main aims of the Hungarian project was to work in tandem with their local RDA National Node to reach out to their target audience of researchers on data management and data repository issues. Of note here is how the project team took into account that research communities often receive a large volume of messages related to open science and research data management best practices; part of the activity of the Hungary project was to streamline and optimise the transfer of messages to their audience. A notable result in this respect was the translation of one of their adopted RDA Recommendations into Hungarian.¹⁹
- The SURFsara project was also concerned with direct engagement with their local community. The first phase of their project²⁰ was to foster a commitment to improve cooperation at the national level and establish a common understanding of research data

¹⁷ The software developed by the project is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3883409>

¹⁸ See Roukema, 2020: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.11779>

¹⁹ <https://openaccess.mtak.hu/index.php/projektek/rda>

²⁰ As outlined here:

https://www.edugroepen.nl/sites/RDM_platform/LCRDM/SiteAssets/Wikipages/Taakgroep%20RDA%27s%2023%20Things/Work%20plan_version%203.pdf

management among diverse practitioners.²¹ The result of this was that the large list of communities and stakeholders identified as worth involving were exposed to the practical benefits of RDA Recommendations and Outputs.

Much of the other engagement of local communities and stakeholders for the other projects was achieved via the communications and dissemination activities outlined above. Though the local environments of each of the funded projects differ in terms of RDA activity and how long their national networks have been established, in all contexts it is necessary for continued and proactive efforts to engage local communities to be made in order for open sharing and research data management practices to be developed and strengthened.

RDA Sustainability & EOSC

The strengthening of community connections links closely to the longer-term sustainability of the work completed as part of these funded projects, as well as to the future sustainability of the RDA in general (see D5.6 Final Sustainability Strategy report for more detail on this).

Three of the grant awards funded the development of a tool or platform that is intended for long-term use. These are:

- **Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias:** 'Maneage' framework: <https://maneage.org/>
- **University of Sofia:** Platform for wheat data and Fusarium data integration: https://github.com/IliyanMihaylov/fusarium_web_plarform
- **SURFSara:** '23 Things revisited: Field guides to Research Data Management': <https://23things.sites.uu.nl/>

Each has plans for the sustainability and maintenance of these resources in place, with the RDA branding and acknowledgement of funding ensuring that the results of the grants will be visible to future users.

For the remaining projects, plans for sustainability are more dependent on the input and support from other organisations. For the CCCA and BSC projects, the key point to note here is that, as they are part of ongoing initiatives, the work done with respect to implementing the Recommendations and Outputs has been successfully embedded in and given prominence by larger service providers. As part of the work undertaken by the project in Hungary, the project team noted in their final report that this grant has been an effective starting point for the process of engagement with local and national data repositories, while work with data publishing and archiving will continue in the frame of the connections with the RDA Hungary National Node and NI4OS-Europe.

This connection with NI4OS-Europe highlights the potential for the future development of the funded projects via engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In a similar fashion, the project at BSC is involved in the EOSC Synergy²² providing a use case of Sand and

²¹ See Jetten et al., 2019: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3337870>

²² <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

Dust Storm data repository to be connected to the EOSC, while the CCCA organisation is involved in the 'Austrian EOSC café', an expert forum for Austrians activities regarding EOSC.²³ The projects funded as part of the RDA Europe 4.0 open call described here, or other projects which may be inspired to adoption RDA Recommendations or Outputs, are in the position to be able to benefit further from and contribute to the EOSC in connection with the funding of adoption grants as part of the INFRAEOSC-03-2020 project.²⁴ For further information on RDA and EOSC cooperation, see the 'EOSC projects survey' section below.

Input to RDA Secretariat adoption activities

Adoption support to secretariat

The Secretariat Adoption task force, which is composed of RDA Europe 4.0 project partners and members of the RDA Secretariat, works on fostering adoption of the RDA Outputs & Recommendation, following three objectives:

1. Enhanced discoverability and intelligibility of RDA recommendations, outputs, and adoption stories:

- **Outputs metadata template:** This template for the outputs, recommendations and adoption stories has been improved and streamlined in collaboration with the web support team, RDA Secretariat and Global Adoption task force.
- **Collection of Adoption Stories:** The collection supported by RDA Europe 4.0 holds 20 stories from organisations around the world to inspire further uptake of the RDA Recommendations and Outputs in written and audiovisual format. See Table 4 below for an overview of these.
- **Recommendations and Outputs Catalogue tool:** This was developed during the RDA Europe 4.0 project to allow for the Recommendations, Supporting Outputs, Outputs in the process of publication to be searched by status, data lifecycle stage, and research domain, allowing for users to be able to locate with ease the RDA Outputs most suitable for their activities.
- **Adoption stories webforms:** A uniform and easily accessible format was set up to collect new Adoption Stories. The webform was developing in two phases, where the first version was more detailed, to be followed up by a more light-weight version to increase the response rate of adopters.
- **DOIs for Adoption Stories:** These were put in place in order to facilitate increased discoverability of these use cases.
- **Printed versions of the Adoption Stories:** These were used for dissemination at RDA P13, P14 and P15, and the RDA nodes meeting at the International Digital Curation Conference in Dublin in February 2020.

²³ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/eosc-building-processes-austria-eosc-cafe>

²⁴ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/infraeosc-03-2020-integration-and-consolidation-existing-pan-european-access-mechanism-public>

Figure 2: Sample of RDA adoption flyer with collection of stories, designed and printed for P15, used for the Global Adoption Week 2020

2. Adoption support through education material development:

- **Webinars** on RDA outputs and Adoption Stories have been organised, including the RDA Global Adoption Week 2020. This was organised as a replacement for the Adoption Session which had been due to take place at the Melbourne Plenary 15 event, with insights and results from the event published on the RDA website²⁵ and further information in Table 3 below. In total, the activity of the RDA project team resulted in a total of 12 webinars and the publication of slides and webinar recordings for each of them.
- **2 Plenary Birds of a Feather (BoF) sessions** on adoption to engage with the RDA community in adoption exercises
- **Plenary adoption sessions** at P12, P13, P14 and P15, turned into the Global Adoption Week 2020, highlighting RDA outputs and recommendations ready for adoption and cases of adoption. See Table 4 below for a detailed overview of outputs, recommendations and adoption highlighted.
- **RDA Outputs Cards:** printable and online sets of factsheets for each of the RDA Recommendations and Outputs. During the RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime, three

²⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-2020-insights>

timestamped sets were released: August 2018, July 2019, March 2020 and a fourth update is foreseen for September 2020 including the cards for the COVID-19 WG.

- **Explainer video** on the RDA outputs and adoption process
- **RDA Call for Adoption stories**: with collection possibilities via webform and video interviews at RDA plenaries and events.

Figure 3: Web banner announcing the publication of slides and recordings of the RDA Global Adoption Week 2020

3. Monitoring and evaluation of adoption impact:

- **RDA overview of use-cases²⁶**: Regular update with cases of adoption and links to adoption stories and projects. In D4.2 in June 2019 75 use cases were reported, at the time of writing August 2020, this number has risen to 137 use-cases, plus a direct link to the CoreTrustSeal interactive map where all additional 90+ certified repositories can be consulted.
- **Connecting the use of RDA outputs and recommendations to RDA**: Publications that include the RDA reference are connected to the RDA Community on ZENODO: *"This work was developed as part of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) 'WG/IG' entitled 'long name (short name)', and we acknowledge the support provided by the RDA community and structures"*
- **Connect & visualise adoption of RDA outputs & recommendations**: RDA Europe 4.0 is working on the OpenAIRE Dashboard and integration to showcase the impact of the RDA adoption activities.

²⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-recommendations>

Plenary adoption sessions

Outputs & adoption sessions are a fixed programme item at each RDA Plenary meeting, aimed at raising awareness of recently published and adoptable outputs with the RDA community. From P12 to P15 the focus has shifted from a presentation moment of recently published outputs, to raising awareness of a wider range of the wide pallet of RDA outputs & recommendations. Table 3 below displays an overview of the adoption sessions supported by RDA Europe 4.0 during the project lifetime.

Table 3: Plenary Session results

Plenary	Description	Outputs & adoption
P12	Discussion panel with 3 speakers raising awareness on adoptable RDA outputs. Speakers were engaged in a discussion on the added value of adoption of the presented outputs and barriers overcome. The audience was engaged in a poll to understand the interest in and barriers to adoption of RDA outputs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CoreTrustSeal ● Scholarly Link Exchange (SCHOLIX) WG - adoption story DataCite ● AGU Enabling FAIR Data - adoption of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data policy standardisation and implementation IG ● An open, universal literature-data cross-linking service - RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG Recommendations ● Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations
P13	<p>Overview & discussion panel: RDA Recommendation & Outputs were presented according to the Research Data Lifecycle, followed by a discussion panel with three chairs and their 3 adopters.</p> <p>Session outputs: Slides overview presentation & recordings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agrisemantics WG & adoption story INRAE ● Data Fitness for use & adoption story CoreTrustSeal ● PID Kernel Information & adopter German Climate Computing Center
P14	Marketplace format: the revamped Adoption and Outputs session in marketplace format aimed to give visibility to disciplinary approaches supported by RDA while providing a great way to network and speak to the discipline drivers: discipline-focused Working and Interest Groups, adopters and promoters of the RDA Recommendations and Outputs, and domain-specific Ambassadors.	6 domain specific, 1 domain agnostic area and 1 CODATA Data Science Journal area with 31 outputs & adoption topics available. The full overview is available here: https://www.rda-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-2020-insights

	Session outputs: Slides & recordings .	
P15	<p>In 5 consecutive days, 10 webinars, 33 speakers from all regions, 19 outputs highlighted, and 13 adoption stories told. The adoption session, originally planned for Plenary 15, turned into a Global Adoption Week which took place from 15-19 June 2020. The aim was to demonstrate the wide variety of adoptable and adopted solutions to data sharing challenges that people in the field encounter in their daily jobs. Daily webinars provided an opportunity to learn about RDA Outputs and engage with speakers from all around the world who created and implemented them in their organisations. Presentations were organised around five themes from the research data lifecycle, as used in the RDA Recommendations and Outputs catalogue.</p> <p>Session outputs: News-item, slides, dedicated Youtube Playlist, RDA Outputs & Recommendations Catalogue posters & edited adoption stories (upcoming September 2020)</p>	<p>19 outputs highlighted and 13 adoption stories told, the full programme overview is available here: https://www.rda-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-15-19-june-2020</p>

Figure 4: Examples of digital posters used to promote Global Adoption Week sessions

Adoption stories

Adoption stories aim to inspire further uptake, Table 4 below provides an extensive overview of the RDA Adoption Stories sourced, edited, designed, published and promoted with the support of RDA Europe 4.0 during the project's lifetime.

Table 4: Adoption Stories published during RDA Europe 4.0

Adoption story	Format	Recommendation/Output	Recommendation /Output published during RDA Europe 4.0	Node, Ambassador Adoption project support
Improving Citation of evolving data in distributed asynchronous infrastructures	Graphic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDA Data Citation WG recommendation RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG Outputs: 	N	RDA France

Adopter: VAMDC				
Data Standards For Agriculture: INRA Adoption Of RDA Outputs Adopter: INRA	Graphic + Upcoming recording RDA Global Adoption Week 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines • Agrisemantics Working Group • Data Fabric's "Recommendations for Implementing a Virtual Layer for Management of the Complete Life Cycle of Scientific Data". • "23 Things: Libraries for Research Data" by the Libraries for Research Data IG • The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations • Data Citation of Evolving data 	Y	RDA France
Towards Sustainable Research Data Repositories Adopter: OECD	Graphic + Upcoming recording RDA Global Adoption Week 2020	Income Streams for Data Repositories report	N	RDA Netherlands
Dynamic Data Citation For Frequently Modifying High Resolution Climate Data Adopter: CCCA	Graphic	RDA Data Citation WG recommendation	N	RDA Austria
Achieving the CoreTrustSeal certification to increase stakeholder confidence Adopter: Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	Graphic	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations ²⁷	Y	RDA Netherlands
Seeking CoreTrustSeal certification to check and expose trustworthiness outside the community boundaries	Graphic	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG	Y	RDA France

²⁷ On 11 September 2017, a single independent entity, the new CoreTrustSeal organisation was announced. From 2018, the CoreTrustSeal is a legal foundation entity under Dutch law.

Adopter: Strasbourg astronomical Data Centre (CDS)		Recommendations		
Building the Reputation as a trusted Repository following international Standards Adopter: Australian Data Archive (ADA)	Graphic	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations	Y	
Building the Reputation as a trusted Repository following international Standards Adopter: Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) Data Access Portal (DAP)	Graphic + Upcoming recording RDA Global Adoption Week 2020	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations	Y	
Improving Data Management Procedures based on CoreTrustSeal Certification Adopter: Chinese Astronomical Data Center	Graphic + Upcoming recording RDA Global Adoption Week 2020	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations	Y	
CoreTrustSeal as a framework underpinning policy and technical development Adopter: Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI)	Graphic	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations	Y	RDA Ireland
An agreed approach to assessing the trustworthiness and quality of SSH data repositories in EOSC Adopter: Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud	Graphic + Upcoming recording RDA Global Adoption Week 2020	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations	Y	
How to make FAIRness and reliability manifest: the	Graphic	Repository Audit And Certification DSA-WDS	N	RDA Germany

CoreTrustSeal for TextGridRep Adopter: DARIAH-DE		Partnership WG Recommendations		
Enabling Open Research Publishing Adopter: Wiley	Audiovisual	The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies	Y	
Making Social Sciences And Humanities' Language Datasets Accessible For Humans And Machines Adopter: CLARIN	Audiovisual	RDA outputs by the Data Fabric IG	N	
Improving Scholarly Communication, Linking Datasets From Institutional Repositories With ScholeXplorer. Adopter: OpenAIRE	Audiovisual	Scholix Metadata Schema for Exchange of Scholarly Communication Links	Y	RDA Italy
Implementing Data Citation On The Earth Observation Data Centre For Water Resource Monitoring (EODC) Adopter: Earth Observation Data Centre (EODC)	Graphic	RDA Data Citation WG Recommendation	N	RDA Austria
NSD DMP – Enabling Long-Term Preservation And Sharing Of Research Data Adopter: Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD)	Graphic	RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans	Y	RDA Norway
Curating A Research Institutional Scholarly Record Connecting Externally Deposited Datasets. Adopter: University of Manchester Library	Audiovisual	Scholix Metadata Schema for Exchange of Scholarly Communication Links	Y	RDA United Kingdom
Enabling FAIR Data In The Earth, Space, And Environmental Sciences	Audiovisual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data policy standardisation and implementation IG 	Y	

Adopter: American Geophysical Union		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An open, universal literature-data cross-linking service - RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG Recommendations Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG Recommendations 		
Embedding Research Data Management Plans In Ethics Approval And Funding Application Processes Adopter: Haplo	Graphic	RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans	Y	RDA United Kingdom
Improving the Copernicus Climate Data Store metadata scheme with the RDA metadata standards repository Adopter: Copernicus via Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC)	Graphic + RDA Spain event recording	Metadata Standards Directory Working Group Recommendations	Y	RDA Spain & Adoption grantee

Adoption stories told during the RDA Global Adoption Week 2020 and virtual RDA Node events, of which recordings will be added to the dedicated RDA adoption stories page <https://www.rda-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>.

Table 5: Global Adoption Week 2020 Adoption Stories

Adoption story	Format	Recommendation / output	Rec / output published during RDA EU 4.0	Node, Ambassador or Adoption project support
SEAGrid Science Gateway: Adoption of the PID Kernel Information and Data Type Registry Utilizing the E-RPID Testbed toward FAIR Scientific Workflows Adopter: SEAGrid	Adoption week 2020 recording	PID Kernel Information and Data Type Registry	Y	-

23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management, an adoption project Adopter: Dutch National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM)	Adoption week 2020 recording	23 Things: Libraries For Research Data (Supporting Output)	N	RDA EU 4.0 adoption grantee
Scalable Dynamic Data Citation Methodology: the CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation Service Adopter: Climate Change Centre Austria (CCCA)	Adoption week 2020 recording	RDA Data Citation recommendation	N	RDA EU 4.0 adoption grantee
39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture the Nutrition Adopter: the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)	Adoption week 2020 recording	39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture the Nutrition	Y	RDA Ambassador Agriculture Caterina Caracciolo
Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components Recommendation - + Introducing Maneage: customizable framework for managing data lineage Adopter: Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC)	Adoption week 2020 recording RDA Spain event recording	RDA/WDS Publishing Data Workflows WG Recommendations	N	RDA EU 4.0 adoption grantee
FAIR data maturity model: specification and guidelines - FAIRsFAIR Adoption story Adopter: FAIRsFAIR	Adoption week 2020 recording	FAIR data maturity model: specification and guidelines	Y	
Learning to share: a road to national data publishing policy Adopters: University of Debrecen & Hungarian Academy of Sciences	Adoption week 2020 recording	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership Working Group • Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components 	N	RDA EU 4.0 adoption grantees

At the time of writing, another three adoption stories are in the editorial process for RDA adoption stories.

RDA Europe National Nodes

Established as part of the RDA Europe 4.0 project, the RDA national nodes in 22 European countries engage with research communities, support national agendas, and aim to increase the uptake of standards and participation in RDA globally. As part of their workplans, all nodes are mandated to foster the adoption of RDA outputs in their regions. This aspect of their work includes outreach to local institutions and national infrastructures to encourage the submission of adoption stories to the RDA Secretariat and articles to the CODATA Data Science Journal special collection on RDA results.

Adoption activities of the national nodes, including KPIs in this area, are monitored and reported via quarterly reports and coordination calls. To date, outreach efforts of the RDA Europe National Nodes have resulted in 13 adoption stories (11 published, with 2 more going through the publication process at the time of writing), with further submissions in progress. The stories already published³⁰ report on the adoption experiences of a range of organisations including repositories, data centres, research information system providers, publishers and universities:

- Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) adoption of the CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification
- Strasbourg astronomical Data Centre (CDS) adoption of the CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification
- Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) adoption of the CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification
- DARIAH-DE (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) adoption of the CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification
- The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) adoption of RDA outputs related to Income Streams for Data Repositories
- The French National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA) adoption of multiple RDA outputs
- The Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Centre (VAMDC) adoption of RDA recommendations for data citation and the Scholix service for exchanging information about links between literature and data. This adoption case was also documented in greater detail in a CODATA Data Science Journal article³¹.
- Haplo adoption of the RDA Common Standard for Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans
- Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD) adoption of the RDA Common Standard for Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans
- University of Manchester Library adoption of the Scholix Metadata Schema for Exchange of Scholarly Communication Links
- Springer Nature adoption of the FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies

³⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>

³¹ <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-004>

- Earth Observation Data Centre for Water Resource Monitoring (EODC) adoption of the Recommendations of the RDA Data Citation Working Group
- The Climate Change Centre Austria (CCCA) Data Centre adoption of the RDA Recommendation on Data Citation of Evolving Data

RDA Ambassadors

Outreach and engagement around adoption has also been supported through the RDA Europe 4.0 Ambassadors programme. The selected domain Ambassadors are group co-chairs or actively involved in discipline focused RDA Working and Interest groups, on the one hand and in their domain communities, on the other. The role has allowed them to establish connections, share knowledge, expertise and provide training in support to the adoption of the wider RDA data sharing solutions in their communities of practice.

Considering discipline specificities, the Ambassadors trailed different approaches:

- Caterina Caracciolo, RDA Europe Ambassador for the Agricultural Sciences, co-chair of the RDA Agrisemantics WG and contributor to the Wheat Data WG, is working with the FAO, e-Rosa project (e-Infrastructure Roadmaps for Open Science in Agricultural and Food Sciences) and GODAN has connected these communities, as well as supported the outreach and adoption of the Agrisemantics Wg output e.g. via a journal paper: “39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture and Nutrition”, Caracciolo et al. Submitted to CODATA Data Science Journal (currently in review process)
- Sebastien Denvil, RDA Europe Ambassador for the Earth Sciences and Climate modelling, has been particularly involved in the ongoing adoption of the CoreTrustSeal at the European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF)
- Nikola Vasijevic, RDA Europe Ambassador for Engineering and Technology / Wind energy, has driven the adoption case of the Persistent Identification of Instruments WG recommendations at the Technical University of Denmark Wind Energy Department (DTU Wind Energy)³²
- Ana Slavec, RDA Europe Ambassador for Engineering / Renewable Materials, has collaborated with the RDA Materials Resource Registries WG on an update to the report produced by the group on the metadata standards for different materials that in its initial version did not acknowledge wood and other biomaterials.
- Fotis Psomopoulos, RDA Europe Ambassador for the Bioinformatics, has been focusing on training aspects and the connection with the ELIXIR via a set of joint courses including the ELIXIR / CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Advanced Workshop on Bioinformatics³³
- Fiona Murphy, RDA Ambassador for Media and Communications, has facilitated discussions on the wider adoption of the Research data policy framework for all journals and publishers (Data policy standardisation and implementation IG) across various

³² <https://github.com/rdawg-pidinst/use-cases/blob/master/16-DTU-Wind-Energy.md>

³³ <https://codata-rda-advanced-bioinformatics-2019.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

publisher frameworks (PLOS, Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley, Taylor & Francis, etc) that come together under the umbrella of the STM collaboration.

CODATA Journal Special Collection

The CODATA Data Science Journal special collection³⁴ gathers and promotes research results and outcomes stemming from the Research Data Alliance activities. In particular, it collects high quality papers describing the latest results of RDA working groups (WGs) or interest groups (IGs) focusing particularly on use cases that highlight the added value of the RDA solutions for different challenges related to research data sharing and management.

The scope of this special collection is to ultimately become a point of reference for experts from the international community that are committed to enabling data sharing, exchange, and interoperability by showcasing the various RDA results and how these have been implemented across disciplines, organisations and geographies.

During its lifetime, the RDA Europe 4.0 project supported the publication of a maximum of 30 articles. Meaning that the publication fees (i.e. Article Processing Charges or 'APCs') were covered by the project, on a first come first served basis. The Call for Papers, as well as funding, was open to all interested applicants regardless of their geographical provenance.

³⁴ CODATA Data Science Journal special collection:
<https://datascience.codata.org/collections/special/research-data-alliance-results/>

Figure 6: CODATA Call for Papers promotional card

During the project lifetime CODATA issued 2 calls for papers, the first opened on 10 July 2018 and closed on 1 September 2018, the second call opened in April 2019 as a continuant call, for which papers submitted by 17 July were eligible for the RDA Europe 4.0 funding of the APC.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, 8 papers have been accepted and published, listed in Table 6 below. One paper has been accepted, awaiting its publication and 19 papers are under review. The Data Science Journal Research Data Alliance special collection editors have indicated the collection will remain open for new papers allowing additional RDA results to be added to the reference collection for data sharing.

Table 6: CODATA DSJ Special Collection publications

Authors	Title	Date	RDA results	Impact
Markus Stocker, Louise Darroch, Rolf Krahl, Ted Habermann, Anusuriya Devaraju, Ulrich Schwardmann, Claudio D'Onofrio, Ingemar Häggström	Research paper: Persistent Identification of Instruments	May 2020	Output of Persistent Identification of Instruments WG (PIDINST)	627 Views 119 Downloads 42 Twitter

Iain Hrynaszkiewicz, Natasha Simons, Azhar Hussain, Rebecca Grant, Simon Goudie	Practice paper: Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers	February 2020	An output of the Data policy standardisation and implementation IG	1831 Views 227 Downloads 1 Citation 100 Twitter
Anne E. Thessen, Matt Woodburn, Dimitrios Koureas, Deborah Paul, Michael Conlon, David P. Shorthouse, Sarah Ramdeen	Research paper: Proper Attribution for Curation and Maintenance of Research Collections: Metadata Recommendations of the RDA/TDWG Working Group	November 2019	Metadata Recommendations of the RDA/TDWG WG	928 Views 109 Downloads 75 Twitter
Stephanie Russo Carroll, Desi Rodriguez-Lonebear, Andrew Martinez	Research paper: Indigenous Data Governance: Strategies from United States Native Nations	July 2019	Output of the Data policy standardisation and implementation IG	1593 Views 446 Downloads 6 Citations 63 Twitter
Sam Grabus, Jane Greenberg	Research paper: The Landscape of Rights and Licensing Initiatives for Data Sharing	July 2019	Identification of the resources best suited for researchers' data sharing need	673 Views 163 Downloads 20 Twitter
Helena Cousijn, Patricia Feeney, Daniella Lowenberg, Eleonora Presani, Natasha Simons	Practice paper: Bringing Citations and Usage Metrics Together to Make Data Count	March 2019	-Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) working group -Data Usage Metrics WG	2075 Views 460 Downloads 8 Citations 92 Twitter
Carlo Maria Zwölf, Nicolas Moreau, Yaye-Awa Ba, Marie-Lise Dubernet	Practice paper: Implementing in the VAMDC the New Paradigms for Data	January 2019	Data Citation Working Group RDA/WDS	397 Views 86 Downloads 2 Citations

	Citation from the Research Data Alliance		Scholarly Link Exchange (Scholix) WG	20 Twitter
Mingfang Wu, Fotis Psomopoulos, Siri Jodha Khalsa, Anita de Waard	Research paper: Data Discovery Paradigms: User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories Mingfang	January 2019	Research Data Alliance (RDA) Interest Group Data Discovery Paradigms	1744 Views 470 Downloads 79 Twitter

Transforming RDA recommendations into standards for public procurement (ICT Technical Specifications)

RDA's goal is to expand awareness and adoption of outputs, and hence their impact, within all regions of the world. RDA is not a standards development organisation (SDO), but has been building synergies with SDOs and similar organisations so that RDA Recommendations can either get a fast track to becoming standards, be incorporated in or contribute to common goals and activities, and overall foster adoption and build trust and engagement in new user communities.

In particular, RDA has been recognised as an authorised organisation to submit potential ICT Technical Specifications to the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP - E02758).

At present, three waves of outputs (for a total of 12 outputs) from RDA Working Groups have been submitted to the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP - E02758) to be recognised as ICT Technical Specifications. These were developed via the clear and transparent RDA process for producing and endorsing outputs as RDA Recommendations:

- **Four RDA Recommendations have been recognised as ICT technical specifications** during the RDA Europe 3.0 project. They are **published in the Official Journal of the European Union** “COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION (EU) 2017/1358” of 20 July 2017 on the identification of ICT Technical Specifications for referencing in public procurement³⁵
- **Four RDA Recommendations have been recognised as ICT technical specifications** during the RDA Europe 3.0 project and RDA is awaiting for their publication. RDA Europe 4.0 has liaised with the MSP to speed up their publication but the **full approval process has been delayed** due to the internal reorganisation of DG GROW
- **A third wave of four RDA Recommendations has been submitted** during the RDA Europe 4.0 project. The RDA Europe 4.0 is still awaiting the results of the assessment.

³⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017D1358>

During the RDA Europe 4.0 project, a **potential fourth wave of four RDA Recommendations ready for submission** to MSP has also been identified. More information can be found in D3.4 Final ICT Technical Specifications & contribution to standards.

Conclusion

Since the publication of the D2.1 RDA Results, Adoption and take-up report on the proposed plans to foster the uptake of RDA results, much effort has been made on a number of different fronts. The sections above have outlined the success of the instruments set up and the contribution of the RDA Europe 4.0 project to the operations of the RDA in its entirety.

Outside of the funded Adoption projects themselves, the adoption and uptake of RDA Recommendations and Outputs has been supported by the activities of the other areas which received RDA Europe 4.0 funding; the RDA National Node network has supported the adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs and has had a hand in the production of a number of Adoption Stories, while the RDA Europe Ambassadors have been directly involved in cases of adoption and have collaborated on further Adoption Stories, as listed above.

As referenced in the conclusion to the D2.1 RDA Results, Adoption and take-up report, one area where attention was needed was in the publicising of adoption via journal papers. With the establishment of the CODATA DSJ Special Collection on RDA results and the support offered by the RDA Europe 4.0 project in the payment of APCs, this has provided a clear impact in the ongoing publication of peer-reviewed articles. The Special Collection will continue beyond the end of the RDA Europe 4.0 project, providing further opportunity for potential adopters of RDA Recommendations and Outputs to publish their results.

In general terms, the RDA Europe 4.0 project has been valuable from the perspective of developing practices to enhance the uptake of RDA Recommendations and Outputs. The lessons that can be taken from the project include:

- Recognition of the advantage of setting out requirements for RDA Nodes and Ambassadors to support the adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs, with the former having specific KPIs to support the production of Adoption Stories from organisations in their localities;
- The benefit of engaging with stakeholders (through surveys, webinars, etc.) to identify barriers to adoption and to address these concerns with the development of relevant use cases and targeted support;
- Similarly, the benefit of engaging with stakeholders to identify organisations who may potentially implement or adopt RDA Recommendations and Outputs;
- For funded Adoption Projects, the appreciation of the support provided by RDA Europe 4.0 project partners to the funded projects on communications, promotion, and dissemination, and the contact at regular intervals throughout the project duration;
- The positive outcomes for the RDA resulting from the inclusion of requirements in the open call for funded Adoption projects to produce reusable deliverables (in this case, in the form

of Adoption Stories and recorded webinars), along with specific, measurable communications and dissemination targets.

- The establishment of practices that can be continued beyond the cessation of the RDA Europe 4.0 project in the fostering of take-up and adoption, i.e., in the activities of the Global Adoption Task Force, in adoption sessions at RDA Plenary events, etc.

The points above are an attempt to summarise the experiences of the RDA Europe 4.0 project partners with a view to providing actionable insights for future efforts to promote the work of the RDA community.